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**Corporate social responsibility as a factor of increasing the competitiveness of
industrial enterprises**

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***Abstract.** The article examines corporate social responsibility as a strategic factor in increasing the competitiveness of enterprises in the context of increased market competition, transformation of the global economy and growing public expectations for business. A comprehensive theoretical and methodological analysis of the essence and evolution of corporate social responsibility is carried out, taking into account modern scientific approaches, in particular the theory of stakeholders, signaling theory and the theory of excess resources. It is noted that the modern development of economic systems is associated with stability and adaptability, and corporate social responsibility is an important factor in reducing risks, strengthening trust and increasing the competitiveness of enterprises. It is substantiated that the integration of social responsibility principles into the strategic management system contributes to the formation of sustainable competitive advantages, strengthening business reputation, increasing investment attractiveness and developing human capital of the enterprise. The paper proposes a structured approach to assessing the impact of corporate social responsibility on internal and external groups of stakeholders. A system of indicators has been developed that reflects the social, environmental and economic aspects of the enterprise's activities from the perspectives of employees, consumers, investors and government agencies. It has been established that the implementation of corporate social responsibility contributes to the reduction of operational risks and costs, the growth of trust from partners, the increase of loyalty of personnel and customers, as well as the strengthening of the enterprise's resilience to external challenges. Particular attention has been paid to identifying barriers to the implementation of corporate social responsibility, including limited financial resources, insufficient regulatory support, weak institutional support and a low level of managerial readiness for social innovations. It has been concluded that corporate social responsibility is not only an ethical guideline for modern business, but also an effective tool for increasing the competitiveness of enterprises, ensuring their long-term sustainable development, adaptability to changes in the external environment and strengthening market positions in modern business conditions.*

***Keywords.** Competitive advantages, corporate social responsibility, competitiveness of enterprises, stakeholder theory, signaling theory, CSR assessment system.*

**Корпоративна соціальна відповідальність як чинник підвищення
конкурентоспроможності промислових підприємств**

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***Анотація.** У статті досліджується корпоративна соціальна відповідальність як стратегічний чинник підвищення конкурентоспроможності підприємств в умовах посилення ринкової конкуренції, трансформації глобальної економіки та зростання суспільних очікувань щодо бізнесу. Проведено комплексний теоретико-методологічний аналіз сутності й еволюції корпоративної соціальної відповідальності з урахуванням сучасних наукових підходів, зокрема теорії заінтересованих сторін, сигнальної теорії та теорії надлишкових ресурсів. Зазначено, що сучасний розвиток економічних систем*

пов'язаний зі стійкістю й адаптивністю, а корпоративна соціальна відповідальність є важливим чинником зниження ризиків, зміцнення довіри та підвищення конкурентоспроможності підприємств. Обґрунтовано, що інтеграція принципів соціальної відповідальності в систему стратегічного управління сприяє формуванню стійких конкурентних переваг, зміцненню ділової репутації, підвищенню інвестиційної привабливості та розвитку людського капіталу підприємства. У роботі запропоновано структурований підхід до оцінювання впливу корпоративної соціальної відповідальності на внутрішні й зовнішні групи заінтересованих сторін. Розроблено систему показників, що відображає соціальні, екологічні та економічні аспекти діяльності підприємства з позицій працівників, споживачів, інвесторів і державних органів. Встановлено, що реалізація корпоративної соціальної відповідальності сприяє зниженню операційних ризиків і витрат, зростанню довіри з боку партнерів, підвищенню лояльності персоналу й клієнтів, а також посиленню стійкості підприємства до зовнішніх викликів. Особливу увагу приділено виявленню бар'єрів упровадження корпоративної соціальної відповідальності, серед яких обмеженість фінансових ресурсів, недостатність нормативно-правового забезпечення, слабка інституційна підтримка та низький рівень управлінської готовності до соціальних інновацій. Зроблено висновок, що корпоративна соціальна відповідальність виступає не лише етичним орієнтиром сучасного бізнесу, а й дієвим інструментом підвищення конкурентоспроможності підприємств, забезпечуючи їхній довгостроковий сталий розвиток, адаптивність до змін зовнішнього середовища та зміцнення позицій на ринку в сучасних умовах господарювання.

Ключові слова. *Конкурентні переваги, корпоративна соціальна відповідальність, конкурентоспроможність підприємств, теорія заінтересованих сторін, сигнальна теорія, система оцінювання КСВ.*

Introduction. In the context of the transformation of the global economy, intensifying competition, and the growing societal expectations placed upon business, corporate social responsibility (CSR) is increasingly gaining importance as a strategic and competitive factor in the sustainable development of enterprises. Modern enterprises are faced with the necessity to consider not only economic, but also social, environmental, and ethical aspects of their activities. Particular attention in contemporary research is devoted to the premise that the development of enterprises and economic systems should be examined in inseparable conjunction with the categories of security, sustainability, and adaptability in the face of escalating external challenges. Within this framework, corporate social responsibility may be interpreted not merely as a means of strengthening a company's competitive position, but also as an effective instrument for risk mitigation, enhancement of adaptive capacity, alignment of the interests of key stakeholder groups, and ensuring long-term sustainable development. In this regard, the study of corporate social responsibility as a factor in enhancing enterprise competitiveness acquires not only applied but also theoretical and methodological significance, as it enables a deeper understanding of its role in shaping a contemporary management model oriented toward efficiency, sustainability, and economic security.

Analysis of Recent Research and Publications

The study of the phenomenon of corporate social responsibility and its impact on enterprise competitiveness is becoming increasingly relevant in the context of growing attention to issues of sustainable development, the ESG agenda, and the social significance of business. The formation of the scientific foundations of CSR dates back to the mid-20th century: the American economist Howard Bowen is considered a pioneer in this field, who in his work "Social Responsibilities of the Businessman" (1953) first articulated the social obligations of business as an integral component of managerial strategy. Subsequently, Archie Carroll (1999) characterized H. Bowen as the founder of the CSR concept, thereby consolidating his contribution to the development of this scientific paradigm. Contemporary interpretations of CSR,

including those presented in the works of Timothy Foran (2001) and Anirban Ghosh (2017), conceptualize it as a set of initiatives and practices aimed at addressing the interests of both internal and external stakeholders, including employees, society, the state, and the natural environment.

In academic literature, significant attention is devoted to the development of theoretical and methodological foundations linking CSR and competitiveness. The evolution of CSR theory has become a crucial stage in understanding its role in business and has laid the groundwork for establishing its connection with competitiveness. Scholars such as Michael L. Barnett and Robert M. Salomon (2012), Edward Freeman (1984), and Michael Spence (1973) have demonstrated that the implementation of CSR contributes to an increase in market value, facilitates the consideration of stakeholder interests, and fosters a positive corporate image, all of which directly influence the competitive advantages of companies.

Contemporary scholarly research significantly expands the understanding of corporate social responsibility as a multifaceted phenomenon, examining its various dimensions in relation to enterprise competitiveness, sustainable development, and strategic management. A substantial contribution to the understanding of the role of CSR in the development of industrial enterprises has been made in the study by Chekulaeva K.A. (2024), who examined the managerial dimension of corporate social responsibility in the industrial sector. The study substantiates that effective CSR management constitutes a prerequisite for the sustainable development of industrial enterprises, contributing to the optimization of internal processes, improvement of corporate governance, and enhancement of organizational adaptability to external challenges.

The direct relationship between social responsibility and the competitive position of an enterprise is analyzed in the dissertation research of Hamuliak R.V. (2026), who interprets CSR as a factor in increasing business competitiveness. The author demonstrates that the systematic implementation of socially responsible practices contributes to strengthening the market position of enterprises through

improved interaction with stakeholder groups, growth of consumer trust, and formation of a positive business image.

An important perspective on corporate social responsibility from the standpoint of its role in ensuring sustainable business development is presented in the work of Bailo V. (2024). The study proves that CSR serves as a strategic guarantee of sustainability, facilitating the alignment of economic, social, and environmental interests of economic entities, reducing risks, and creating conditions for long-term stability and growth of enterprises.

The instrumental nature of CSR within the framework of enterprise development strategies is examined in the study by Budko O.V. et al. (2023), who analyze corporate social responsibility as a tool of business strategy. The authors identify key models and programs of CSR implementation, substantiate the importance of evaluating the effectiveness of socially responsible activities, and propose a comprehensive approach to CSR assessment that takes into account economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic dimensions of corporate activity.

The European integration dimension of corporate social responsibility is explored in the work of Bukreieva D.V. et al. (2022), who examine CSR as a foundation for ensuring business activity in the context of Ukraine's integration into the European economic space. The study emphasizes that the adoption of European standards of socially responsible conduct contributes to the expansion of partnership networks, strengthening of business reputation, and enhancement of enterprise competitiveness in international markets.

The management of corporate social responsibility as a factor of sustainable development is investigated in the work of Lyska P. (2023). The author identifies the principal stakeholders of socially responsible activity, defines their expectations and needs, and proposes a set of practical measures within the framework of CSR management aimed at satisfying stakeholder interests and increasing the competitiveness of enterprises.

The interrelation between entrepreneurial culture and corporate social responsibility in the context of regional economic development is examined in the study by Medynska T.V. et al. (2026). The research substantiates that organizational culture evolves from an internal declaration of values toward a dynamic system grounded in ethics, initiative, and the capacity to create shared value for society. The authors analyze practical business cases of CSR implementation, demonstrating that the synergy of high entrepreneurial culture and effective CSR mechanisms creates a foundation for sustainable regional economic development.

The issue of barriers and drivers of strategic management of CSR consolidation at industrial enterprises of Ukraine is addressed in the work of Pop V.V. (2025). The study systematizes the key obstacles impeding the integration of socially responsible practices into corporate strategies, including insufficient regulatory support, limited financial resources, weak corporate culture, and resistance to change. At the same time, the author identifies drivers capable of catalyzing positive transformations, such as the growing demands of international markets, the expansion of ESG strategies, and the development of innovative management tools.

The principles of sustainable development management as a strategic benchmark for enhancing enterprise competitiveness are investigated in the study by Medianyuk Y. (2025). The author reveals the essence of sustainable development as a strategic concept aimed at ensuring long-term stability through the balanced realization of economic, environmental, and social objectives, and proposes a conceptual model of an integrated strategy for embedding sustainability principles across all levels of enterprise activity.

The role of corporate social responsibility in ensuring the sustainable development of enterprises, with a focus on identifying contemporary challenges and potential opportunities, is examined in the work of Blyzniuk T.P. et al. (2025). The study demonstrates that the integration of CSR contributes not only to the improvement of financial performance but also to the creation of additional value for society through the implementation of social initiatives, support for local communities, and the

achievement of environmental sustainability, thereby confirming that CSR serves as an effective instrument for the long-term resilience and adaptability of enterprises.

Unresolved Aspects of the Overall Problem

Despite the growing interest in issues of corporate social responsibility (CSR), in practice there remains a lack of comprehensive methodological approaches that make it possible to assess the impact of social responsibility on the competitiveness of enterprises, especially in the industrial sector. In this regard, the relevance of the present study is обусловлена... excuse me, conditioned by the need to develop a structured model for assessing the impact of CSR on the key elements of the competitive environment, as well as to identify tools that contribute to enhancing the sustainability and market efficiency of enterprises.

The aim of the study is to identify and substantiate the influence of corporate social responsibility on increasing the competitiveness of industrial enterprises, as well as to develop a methodological approach for assessing the impact of CSR on various stakeholder groups in the context of sustainable development.

Research Methodology

The theoretical and methodological basis of this article consists of works in the field of general economic literature and studies on corporate social responsibility at industrial enterprises, covering a wide range of issues, from theoretical concepts to practical methods and instruments. These studies play an important role in the formation and implementation of effective corporate social responsibility programs. The research methodology is based on a comparative analysis of international and national practices of CSR implementation. The methods used include content analysis, a systems approach, and comparative analysis.

Presentation of the Main Research Findings

Over the past decade, the concept of corporate social responsibility (CSR) has undergone significant development and has transformed from an auxiliary business practice into a strategically important element of the activities of companies of various sizes and industries. The influence of CSR extends far beyond corporate governance

and marketing alone. It actively shapes new approaches and methods in applied academic disciplines such as strategic management, organizational behavior, and competitiveness management [1]. In the modern context, CSR is viewed not only as a tool for building a positive image or minimizing reputational risks, but as a key factor in creating long-term value and sustainable competitive advantage. This is confirmed both by theoretical studies and by practical approaches to company management and development [2].

The integration of CSR into the enterprise development strategy is becoming an integral part of the modern business model. Empirical research in the fields of corporate governance and CSR confirms that incorporating social responsibility into the strategy of an economic entity brings a number of practical benefits. In particular, an important role is played by Stakeholder Theory, formulated by Edward Freeman (Freeman, 1984). According to this concept, the active development of CSR makes it possible to balance the interests of various groups of shareholders, employees, customers, suppliers, local communities, and government authorities involved in business processes, which in turn leads to increased financial performance and an improved competitive position of the enterprise.

Further development of views on the impact of CSR on business is based on signaling theory, proposed by Michael Spence (Spence, 1973) in the context of information asymmetry. According to this theory, corporate actions in the field of CSR serve as a positive signal to external stakeholders, especially investors, demonstrating the reliability, ethical responsibility, and strategic maturity of the company. Modern researchers, such as Jones D.A. and Willness C.R. (Jones & Willness, 2013), clarify that through CSR an organization communicates its values, reputation, and prosocial orientation, thereby forming an attractive image in the eyes of employees, partners, and investors. At the same time, resource slack theory emphasizes that enterprises possessing excess resources are able to invest in CSR projects that minimize political, legal, and social risks, thereby contributing to the growth of financial stability.

Studies of corporate social responsibility as a factor in enhancing enterprise competitiveness in contemporary scientific literature demonstrate a gradual transition from a general understanding of CSR as an ethical norm of doing business to its interpretation as a systemic managerial tool capable of influencing the market position of an enterprise, its reputation, investment attractiveness, personnel stability, and long-term sustainability. At the same time, scientific approaches increasingly emphasize not only the acknowledgment of the positive impact of CSR on enterprise performance, but also the need to develop appropriate analytical tools for its evaluation in relation to competitiveness.

Work [1] examines global trends in the development of business social responsibility, which makes it possible to consider CSR as an objective component of the modern economic model. The authors focus on the growing role of environmental, social, and ethical standards in corporate activities, as well as on the integration of responsible business principles into corporate strategies. The study forms a theoretical foundation for understanding CSR as a multidimensional phenomenon whose effectiveness cannot be assessed solely through individual social initiatives. On the contrary, global trends indicate the feasibility of using a systemic approach, according to which CSR assessment should cover various areas of responsible corporate activity and take into account its impact on stakeholders.

The relationship between social responsibility and competitiveness is most substantively disclosed in study [3], where business social responsibility is directly defined as a factor in enhancing competitiveness. The work substantiates that the implementation of CSR principles contributes to strengthening the business reputation of an enterprise, increasing trust among consumers and partners, improving the internal social climate, enhancing staff motivation, and generally increasing the effectiveness of economic activity. At the same time, interpreting CSR as a competitiveness factor objectively requires a transition from qualitative characteristics to the quantitative measurement of its manifestations. Therefore, the provisions of this work provide grounds for the conclusion that the analysis of enterprise competitiveness should be

supplemented by a system of indicators that makes it possible to assess the level of CSR development and its impact on the key parameters of the functioning of the economic entity.

Article [4] examines corporate social responsibility through the prism of prospects and opportunities for its implementation in small and medium-sized enterprises in Ukraine. The author proves that CSR is important not only for large corporations but also for SMEs, as it contributes to the formation of a positive image, improvement of interaction with clients, growth of staff loyalty, and strengthening of market positions. This approach is important for forming the methodological basis of the study, since it indicates the need for an adaptive nature of CSR assessment. Accordingly, the system of indicators should not be limited to universal criteria but should be suitable for use by enterprises of different sizes and should take into account the specifics of CSR implementation in various groups of economic entities.

Study [5] interprets corporate social responsibility as a guarantee of sustainable business development. The author emphasizes that CSR ensures the alignment of economic, social, and environmental interests, contributes to risk reduction, strengthens trust in the enterprise, and creates prerequisites for its long-term stability. The importance of this approach lies in the fact that it expands the boundaries of CSR analysis, moving it from the sphere of individual social initiatives to the sphere of systemic management of enterprise sustainability. This, in turn, requires the construction of a system of indicators that makes it possible to take into account not only the internal results of a socially responsible corporate policy but also its external effects, primarily for consumers, investors, the local community, and other stakeholders.

In the monograph by O.M. Hrybinenko [6], attention is focused on the fact that the modern development of economic systems should be considered in close connection with sustainability and the ability to adapt under conditions of growing external and internal challenges. In this context, corporate social responsibility acquires special significance, as it contributes to risk reduction, strengthening stakeholder trust,

increasing enterprise adaptability, and forming sustainable competitive advantages. This approach provides grounds for considering CSR as an important factor in enhancing enterprise competitiveness, ensuring the alignment of economic, social, and environmental priorities within the system of modern management.

Thus, the analysis of the cited sources indicates that in contemporary scientific thought corporate social responsibility is regarded as a multicomponent factor capable of ensuring the formation of competitive advantages of an enterprise through its impact on reputation, effectiveness of interaction with personnel, the level of trust among consumers, investors, and other stakeholders. At the same time, research mainly focuses on the substantive, functional, and strategic aspects of CSR, whereas the issue of comprehensive assessment of its level in relation to enterprise competitiveness requires further methodological development.

In view of this, based on the analyzed theoretical provisions and empirical data, a methodological approach has been developed to form a system of indicators for assessing corporate social responsibility, which is applied in the process of analyzing the competitiveness level of enterprises. Such an approach should be oriented toward taking into account the interests of both internal and external actors employees, investors, consumers, and other stakeholders which will allow for a more complete and objective determination of the role of CSR in shaping modern competitive advantages of an enterprise.

In particular, a comprehensive system of indicators for CSR assessment oriented toward internal stakeholder groups has been proposed (Table 1).

Table 1

Comprehensive System for Assessing Corporate Social Responsibility of an Enterprise from the Perspective of Internal Stakeholders

Group of Factors	Indicators
Social	Psychological: – employee satisfaction with wages and working conditions; – level of workplace conflict;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -proportion of employees receiving non-material incentives (awards, commendations, etc.); -degree of employee satisfaction with communication and feedback from management; -employee engagement index in corporate culture and activities; <p>Professional:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -training expenditures; -ratio of qualification grades to position levels; -number of employees promoted; -number of employees who completed professional development training; <p>Corporate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -staff turnover rate; -proportion of employees owning company shares; -personnel support measures for housing acquisition; -enterprise participation in non-state pension provision; -level of transparency of corporate governance and employee involvement in decision-making; -availability of social support programs for employees and their families; <p>Medical:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -expenditures on employee health improvement (sanatorium treatment); -financing of voluntary health insurance; -occupational morbidity rate; -mortality associated with hazardous working conditions; -total expenditures on general medical care; -number and quality of preventive health protection measures; -employee satisfaction index with company medical support;
<p>Environmenta 1</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - proportion of employees working in hazardous conditions; - number of occupational accidents; - financing of environmental safety and occupational health measures; - ratio of green space area to the total enterprise territory; - implementation of programs to reduce the enterprise's negative environmental impact; - level of environmental awareness and employee involvement in environmental initiatives;
<p>Economic</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -employee retention rate; -level of investment in human capital development; -share of bonus fund in the organization's total profit; -volume of delayed wage payments in the total wage amount;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –level of social contributions (insurance, benefits package) in the profit structure; –growth rate of average wages; –ratio of social package costs to total production expenses.
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(Developed by the authors based on 1, 3, 4, 5, 6)

The proposed system of corporate social responsibility indicators is oriented toward internal stakeholders, primarily the enterprise’s personnel, and can be used both for internal audits of social policy and for the preparation of non-financial reporting within the ESG framework. It makes it possible to objectively assess the level of a company’s social responsibility in the context of working conditions, opportunities for professional development, the degree of involvement in corporate culture, as well as the quality of medical and environmental support provided to employees.

At the same time, the effective implementation of CSR is impossible without taking into account the interests of external stakeholders, such as investors, consumers, government authorities, and society as a whole. Accordingly, to assess the impact of CSR on these groups, a separate comprehensive system of indicators has been developed (Table 2), reflecting the social, environmental, and economic aspects of corporate activity from the perspective of external stakeholders.

Table 2

Comprehensive System for Assessing Corporate Social Responsibility of an Enterprise from the Perspective of External Stakeholders

Group of Factors	Indicators
Investors	
Social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –level of employee satisfaction with working conditions (surveys); –number of corporate volunteer initiatives; –proportion of employees with higher education (in management); –proportion of professionally trained workers; –staff turnover rate at the enterprise; –expenditures on participation in social projects affecting the enterprise’s image;

Environmental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –number of implemented environmentally friendly technologies; –level of reduction in greenhouse gas emissions during the reporting period; –expenditures on pollution prevention (% of net profit); –environmental protection expenditures (% of net profit);
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –return on invested capital; –ratio of operating expenses to total revenue; –enterprise market share relative to the industry leader; –share of dividends distributed to participants in net profit; –proportion of employee-owned shares in total shares; –coefficient of outpacing growth of labor productivity compared to income per employee;
Customers	
Social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –level of customer satisfaction with products (surveys); –proportion of products with quality and safety certificates; –number of social projects involving the enterprise; –number of complaints regarding product quality;
Environmental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –level of recycling and disposal of production waste; –use of environmentally friendly packaging (% of total product volume); –proportion of environmentally friendly raw materials in product cost; –share of defective products in total output; –share of premium-quality products in total output; –expenditures on product licensing and certification;
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –dynamics of product price changes during crisis conditions; –proportion of products sold through loyalty programs; –volume of enterprise investments in improving product quality;
Government Authorities	
Social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –number of social programs implemented jointly with the government; –share of new jobs created through entrepreneurship development; –volume of investments in entrepreneurship development; –proportion of young specialists; –proportion of women in the workforce; –expenditures on employee professional development;
Environmental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –level of compliance with environmental legislation;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">–volume of reduction in production waste and atmospheric emissions;–degree of compliance with environmental standards;–volume of emissions and waste per unit of output;
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none">–level of tax revenues to the state budget;–volume of investments in infrastructure;–share of public procurement;–dynamics of economic efficiency within government programs;–number of joint government and corporate projects implemented;–level of transparency of the enterprise’s financial reporting.

(Developed by the authors based on 1,2,6)

Thus, the conducted analysis confirms that corporate social responsibility encompasses a wide range of aspects of enterprise interaction with both internal and external stakeholders. Internal CSR stakeholders primarily include employees, whose interests are associated with the provision of decent working conditions, opportunities for professional growth, the development of corporate culture, as well as access to medical and environmental benefits. Effective management of these aspects contributes to the creation of a favorable social climate within the organization, increased staff motivation, reduced turnover, and, consequently, higher labor productivity.

On the other hand, external stakeholders such as investors, consumers, government authorities, and the public assess the level of corporate social responsibility from the standpoint of openness, investment reliability, product quality, compliance with environmental standards, and participation in social initiatives. Meeting the expectations of these groups ensures the company’s stable market position, increased public trust, and the possibility of attracting additional resources.

Thus, comprehensive consideration of the interests of both internal and external groups makes it possible to form a balanced and strategically oriented model of corporate governance based on the principles of sustainable development. Such an approach not only enhances the company’s business reputation and image but also helps identify vulnerable areas in the management system, develop competitive

advantages, and ensure long-term stability amid growing demands for transparency and social engagement in business.

The development of enterprise competitiveness under modern economic conditions requires a new level of interaction between business, government, and society based on trust, transparency, and social responsibility. Corporate social responsibility becomes a key element of this model, contributing to the strengthening of business reputation, growth of market capitalization, and formation of sustainable competitive advantages [5, 7].

The relationship between corporate social responsibility and company competitiveness represents a complex research object, involving the analysis of the impact of social and environmental practices on key market indicators and social development [8]. At the same time, corporate social activity generates competitive advantages, including improved image, reduced operating costs, increased loyalty of consumers and personnel, and access to investment resources.

Empirical evidence confirms that a high level of social activity positively correlates with trust and preference from consumers and investors. The development of human capital is a significant factor in enhancing competitiveness, especially when motivational programs and flexible social packages are implemented [9]. Thus, CSR becomes a strategic resource that ensures sustainable enterprise development, particularly under conditions of intensifying market competition.

Based on the analysis of theoretical and empirical studies, key directions through which corporate social responsibility influences the competitiveness of industrial enterprises can be identified. The main competitiveness stakeholders targeted by CSR include consumers, suppliers, banks, employees, investors, and competitors. The influence extends to both internal and external elements of the business environment, forming sustainable socio-economic relationships. The implementation of CSR policy manifests itself in multifaceted positive effects that strengthen the company's market position.

The implementation of CSR policy results in comprehensive positive effects that significantly influence the company's competitive position. These include:

- strengthening business reputation and corporate image;
- enhancement of intellectual capital;
- reduction of administrative and operating costs;
- increase in business value;
- greater transparency and openness of activities;
- increased loyalty of employees and customers;
- expansion of investment opportunities.

In addition, sustainable interaction with stakeholders contributes to the strengthening of social ties, the formation of institutional trust, and the positioning of the enterprise as a socially responsible and reliable partner. Support and development of human capital, including the creation of motivational programs and flexible social packages, is considered an important resource of enterprise competitiveness. Sustainable stakeholder engagement makes it possible not only to enhance internal social stability but also to ensure external recognition of the enterprise as a socially responsible and trustworthy partner.

Consequently, CSR becomes a strategic instrument that ensures sustainable company development and facilitates adaptation to dynamically changing market conditions. In the context of intensifying competition, globalization, and stricter regulatory requirements, corporate social responsibility becomes an important element of sustainable enterprise development.

The generalization of the analysis results made it possible to identify the key directions of CSR influence on enterprise competitiveness and to present them in the form of a structured scheme (Fig. 1). The implementation of CSR policy manifests itself in comprehensive positive effects that significantly affect the company's market position.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Model of the Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility on Enterprise Competitiveness (*developed by the authors*)

The proposed conceptual model (Fig. 1) demonstrates the multi-aspect nature of the influence of CSR on enterprise competitiveness, including the social,

environmental, and economic components of corporate activity. Such a comprehensive systemic approach makes it possible to identify vulnerable areas in a timely manner, develop adaptive management mechanisms, and enhance innovative potential, which in turn contributes to strengthening the company's market position.

To build a comprehensive system for assessing the impact of CSR mechanisms on enterprise competitiveness, it is advisable to rely on a stakeholder-based approach. This approach предполагает... meaning it involves a differentiated analysis of the impact of CSR on various stakeholder groups involved in the functioning of the enterprise, taking into account their specific interests and roles in ensuring the sustainable development of the organization. Table 3 presents a structured characterization of the subjects of the competitive environment, including a system of indicators for their assessment, instruments and mechanisms of CSR influence on competitiveness, as well as the expected positive effects resulting from the implementation of the relevant initiatives.

Table 3

**Indicators, Implementation Mechanisms, and Positive Effects of CSR
Impact on Competitiveness Stakeholders**

Competitiveness Stakeholder	CSR Impact Assessment Indicators	CSR Implementation Tools and Mechanisms	Expected Positive Effects
Consumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none">– share of environmentally certified products;– level of customer satisfaction;– number of complaints and claims;– participation in social projects;	<ul style="list-style-type: none">– promotion of products with enhanced social and environmental value;– consumer involvement in CSR initiatives;– transparent information on product composition and impact;	<ul style="list-style-type: none">– increased customer loyalty;– brand strengthening;– sales growth and market share retention;

Suppliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – stability of partnership relations; – number of long-term contracts; – supplier evaluation based on ethical criteria; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – supplier code of ethics; – sustainable procurement policy; – joint CSR initiatives; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – reduction of logistics and commercial risks; – improvement in the quality of supplied resources; – strengthening of the supply chain;
Banks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – credit history; – level of reporting transparency; – level of tax discipline; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – financial and non-financial reporting (including ESG indicators); – participation in sustainable finance programs; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – increased investment attractiveness; – simplified access to financing; – reduced cost of borrowed capital;
Employees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – level of engagement and satisfaction; – share of expenditures on social programs; – staff turnover index; – investment in training and development; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – development of non-material motivation programs; – creation of an inclusive and safe working environment; – medical and social support; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – increased labor productivity; – reduced staff turnover; – formation of a sustainable human resource potential;
Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – return on invested capital; – degree of ESG strategy implementation; – frequency of non-financial disclosure; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – implementation of sustainable development standards (ISO, GRI, etc.); – publication of non-financial reports; – participation in high-reputation social projects; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – increased interest from responsible investors; – growth of market capitalization; – formation of long-term investment attractiveness;
Competitors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – market positioning; – level of innovativeness; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – partnerships in industry CSR practices; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – strengthened image within the professional community;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">– participation in collective industry initiatives;– media citation frequency;	<ul style="list-style-type: none">– development of joint codes of conduct;– public coverage of social activities;	<ul style="list-style-type: none">– increased market entry barriers;– creation of sustainable differentiation;
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(Developed by the authors)

Conclusions

The conducted analysis confirms that corporate social responsibility exerts a comprehensive impact on key stakeholder groups, both internal and external, that shape the enterprise's competitive environment. The development of CSR indicators and implementation tools makes it possible to design differentiated management approaches that strengthen interaction with each category of stakeholders. For each category consumers, suppliers, banks, employees, investors, and competitors specific CSR mechanisms are implemented aimed at building long-term trust, reducing risks, and increasing the value of cooperation with the company.

This study proposes the implementation of a set of measures aimed at the systemic development of CSR, namely:

1. Development and implementation of a unified industry methodology for assessing CSR level, taking into account both internal and external aspects of enterprise activity. Such a methodology should be based on a comprehensive analysis of key indicators presented in Tables 1–3, ensuring objectivity and comparability of assessment results and enabling the identification of priority areas for improving social policy.

2. Organization of systematic training and professional development programs for managers and specialists in the field of CSR, including the integration of relevant disciplines into university curricula and the development of corporate training. This will enhance competencies and ensure effective implementation of social initiatives.

3. Regular empirical studies on the impact of CSR on enterprise competitiveness and publication of analytical reports and rankings of socially responsible companies.

Such measures increase transparency and motivate businesses toward sustainable development while strengthening corporate image and stakeholder trust.

The proposed structure of evaluation indicators and CSR implementation mechanisms contributes to more accurate diagnostics of the impact zones of corporate social policy and creates preconditions for improving long-term competitiveness.

In conclusion, corporate social responsibility should be emphasized as a key strategic factor for ensuring sustainable development and enhancing enterprise competitiveness. Theoretical analysis and empirical evidence confirm that successful CSR implementation requires a comprehensive and systemic approach that takes into account the interests of all stakeholders. The developed conceptual framework considers CSR as a multidimensional instrument for increasing competitiveness, providing differentiated influence on key groups within the competitive environment.

Thus, the application of a comprehensive and adaptive approach to CSR implementation contributes to the formation of sustainable competitive advantages, strengthening of business reputation, and creation of favorable conditions for long-term organizational development in a dynamically changing market environment.

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